

Trichloroacetic Acid 90% versus Radiofrequency Ablation in the Management of Facial Seborrhic Keratoses: A Prospective Interventional Study

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Abstract:

Introduction: Seborrhic Keratoses (SK) are commonly encountered benign epidermal tumors characterized by well-demarcated, skin coloured to brown or black coloured, slightly elevated papules or plaques. Facial involvement is often associated with cosmetic concerns in patients.

Aims and Objectives: The aim of this study was to compare the efficacy and safety profile of RF ablation with 90% TCA for the treatment of facial SK.

Materials & Methods: A total of 80 cases of facial seborrhic keratosis were included in the study. Group A included SK lesions treated with 90% TCA while Group B included SK lesions treated with RF ablation. Patient satisfaction was measured at three months following the completion of the treatment using a four-point scale.

Results: In group A, 19 patients (47.5%) were completely satisfied, while in group B, 26 patients (65%) were completely satisfied. Thus, patient satisfaction rate was much higher in group B, however, statistically insignificant.

Keywords: Seborrhic Keratoses, Trichloroacetic Acid, Radio-Frequency Ablation.

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Introduction

Seborrhic Keratoses (SK) are commonly encountered benign epidermal tumors characterized by well-demarcated, skin coloured to brown or black coloured, slightly elevated papules or plaques [1]. Facial involvement is often associated with cosmetic concerns in patients. The choice of treatment depends on the number, location, thickness of lesions and overall aesthetic considerations [1,2]. Still, there is paucity of literature on the uniform guidelines to treat SK especially on aesthetically important areas like face. Role of 90% trichloroacetic acid (TCA) and Radiofrequency (RF) ablation has already been described individually in the literature [3]. However, there is scarcity of data on the comparative evaluation of these two modalities in SK.

Aims and Objectives: The aim of this study was to compare the efficacy and safety profile of RF ablation with 90% TCA for the treatment of facial SK.

Materials and Methods

A total of 80 cases of facial seborrhic keratosis were included in the study. Hyperpigmented

elevated palpable lesions of < 1 cm in diameter in size were included in the study. Patients above 30 years of age with at least four lesions with such characteristics regarding their size, pigmentation and texture on face and without any history of concurrent or previous treatment in the past 3 months were included in the study. Patients with history of oral or topical retinoid use in past one month, history of keloid or hypertrophic scar formation, bleeding disorders, connective tissue disease, active skin infections at the site of lesion, active pregnancy and lactation, clinical lesions suspicious of malignancy (atypical, rapidly growing, sudden change in color, eruptive SK lesions) and those who were not willing or available for a follow-up period of at least 2 months were excluded from the study. The subjects were randomly allocated in two groups. Group A included SK lesions treated with 90% TCA while Group B included SK lesions treated with RF ablation.

In group A, 90% TCA solution was applied to the lesion uniformly with application of petroleum jelly around the lesion to prevent excess dripping. Subsequent sessions were repeated at an interval of

2 weeks, if required, to a maximum of three sessions. In group B, patients were subjected to RF ablation in which electrodesiccation was performed by the fine tipped electrode. End point of treatment was determined either by the ablation of the lesion or by the appearance of pinpoint bleeding. Subsequent sessions of RF ablation were given at two weeks intervals till cure was achieved or to a maximum of three sessions. The response to treatment was assessed as complete response (100% clearance of lesion and appearance of normal skin), partial response (>50 to 99% reduction in hyperpigmentation and thickness of lesion) and inadequate or no response (<50% reduction in hyperpigmentation and thickness of lesion). Patient satisfaction was measured at three months following the completion of the treatment using a four-point scale (one - minimally, two - somewhat, three - mostly, four - completely satisfied). Statistical analysis was done using unpaired *t* test and chi-square test. *P* Values less than 0.05 were considered significant.

Results:

Out of 40 patients in Group A, 18 patients were male and 22 were female. Similarly, in group B, 21 patients were male and 19 patients were females. The age ranged from 33 to 65 years with mean age of 45.22 years in group A and 34 to 66 years with mean age of 44.42 years in group B. Duration of lesion varied from 2 months to 6 years in both the groups. At 3 months of follow up, in group A (90% TCA), 18 (45%) cases showed complete clearance, 11 (27.5%) showed partial clearance and 11 (27.5%) showed inadequate response (Figure 1 & 2). In group B (RF ablation), 26 (65%) patients showed complete clearance, 10 (25%) showed partial clearance and 4 (10%) showed inadequate response (Figure 3 & 4). Thus, the rate of clearance was comparable in both the groups ($p=0.09$)

(Figure 5). There was no significant correlation between the duration of lesions and rate of clearance in both the groups ($p>0.05$).

Number of sessions was significantly lesser in group B (mean \pm SD equal 1.10 ± 0.45) than in 90% TCA group (mean \pm SD equal 1.82 ± 0.81) ($p=0.001$). The downtime was 8.24 ± 1.28 days and 11.12 ± 2.05 days in group A and B respectively. Statistically significant lesser downtime was observed in group A ($p=0.001$).

Side effects noted in group A were burning sensation in all (100%) cases, erythema in 25 (62.5%), and crusting in 4 (10%) cases. Post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation was observed in 12 cases (30%), however, no scarring was seen. The major side effects noted in group B were post ablation erythema in 22 (55%) and pain in 14 (35%) cases. Post inflammatory hyperpigmentation and scarring were noted in 3 (7.5%) and 4 (10%) patients respectively. (Figure 6)

In group A, 19 patients (47.5%) were completely satisfied, while in group B, 26 patients (65%) were completely satisfied. Thus, patient satisfaction rate was much higher in group B, however, statistically insignificant.

Role of RF ablation in seborrheic keratosis is attributed to the heat based coagulation of proteins with minimum collateral damage resulting in precise ablation which results in minimum adverse effects and scarring [4,5]. This provides favourable cosmetic results specifically in delicate areas. However, scarring and post hyperpigmentation have been reported in a few cases [5]. Topical trichloroacetic acid works by chemical ablation leading to target destruction of keratinocytes. Incomplete removal of lesions and post inflammatory hyperpigmentation are common especially in Indian skin type. [6,7]

Figure 1: Healing with post inflammatory hyperpigmentation in group A

Figure 2: Partial clearance of seborrheic keratosis in group A

Figure 3: Complete clearance of seborrheic keratosis in group B

Figure 4: Complete clearance of seborrheic keratosis in group B

Figure 5: Rate of clearance in two groups

Figure 6: Adverse effects in two groups

Discussion:

Since, there are currently no standardized guidelines for the treatment of seborrheic keratosis, new treatment modalities are being tested. Gruel et al.[8] conducted a study comparing the effectiveness of erbium: YAG laser and cryosurgery in seborrheic keratoses and observed complete healing in all of the lesions treated with

Er: YAG lasers, while 68% lesions healed in the cryotherapy group. Similarly, Agrawal et al.[9] conducted a unblinded, comparative interventional study comparing the efficacy of 30% H₂O₂ (group A) with 50% trichloroacetic acid (group B) showing clearance in 41.8% of patients in group A and in 23.8% in group B. In a study by Zaresharifi et al. [5] conducted to assess the efficacy and safety

of cryotherapy, electrodesiccation, CO2 laser, and Er: YAG laser in the treatment of seborrheic keratosis, the improvement rate was significantly higher in the CO2, Er: YAG lasers and electrodesiccation group compared to the cryotherapy ($p < 0.001$). However, no significant difference was observed in post-treatment pigmentation and texture between the groups ($p > 0.05$). Similarly, Kalegowda et al. [10] conducted a study on the use of topical trichloroacetic acid versus cryotherapy in the treatment of seborrheic keratoses. Out of 60 patients treated, at the end of 6 months, 91.6 % (55) showed excellent response in the TCA group, 75% (45) showed excellent response, 25%(15) good response in the cryotherapy group.

The present study is first of its kind to compare RF ablation and 90% TCA in seborrheic keratosis. Both RF ablation and 90% TCA were equally efficacious. However, RF ablation can be used as a one-step procedure for seborrheic keratosis in patients with high cosmetic expectations. Patient satisfaction rate was more in RF ablation. However, downtime was less in the 90% TCA group. Mean number of sittings required for clearance of lesions was less for RF ablation as compared to chemical cauterization with 90% TCA. Most common adverse effects in group A and B were burning sensation and erythema respectively. Although no major adverse effects were observed in the two groups, post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation was more common in 90% TCA group as compared to scarring which was noted after RF ablation only.

Conclusion:

Although both the treatment modalities achieved good results, RF ablation showed better results than 90% TCA with better patient satisfaction rates but more downtime. Also, no major adverse effects were observed in the two groups. However, post inflammatory hyperpigmentation was more common in 90% TCA group.

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